
COUNCIL ON
LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
TWENTY-EIGHTH
ANNUAL REPORT/1984

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1785 Massachusetts Ave., N.W.
Washington, D.C. 20036

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine*. . . Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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Fred C. Cole
John A. Humphry

2. Deceased, February 1984.

3. Mr. Humphry was elected to succeed Mr. Cole at the November 1983 Directors' meeting.

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 Jane A. Rosenberg, *Program Associate*
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 James L. Tew, *Accountant*
 Mary Agnes Thompson, *Assistant to the President;*
Secretary and Treasurer

4. Beginning in May 1984.

5. Beginning in January 1984.

6. Beginning in February 1984.

7. Resigned in February 1984.

Memorial to Louis Booker Wright

This tribute to Louis B. Wright, written by Caryl Haskins, was presented at the June 1984 meeting of the Directors of the Council. The accompanying resolution was adopted at that meeting.

In paying tribute to Louis Wright this morning, it seems to me that we are not so much mourning the loss of an inspired and inspiring colleague, whose service and inspiration to the Council have meant so much over all the years since its founding, as expressing our thanks at the freeing of a great and sparkling and untrammled and altogether wonderful spirit. That spirit will live as long as we his friends live to celebrate it—in our memories, in his rare and classical autobiographical books *Barefoot in Arcadia* and *Of Books and Men*, and in his wide-ranging public service.

We in the Council take special note of all that he brought at the most critical levels and in the most critical ways, through its whole life. As members of the Board—and perhaps particularly Fred Cole—will vividly recall, it was Louis who was instrumental in convening the meetings in 1955 that led to the formation of the Council, and for the following twenty-seven years he served as its vice chairman. Council affairs were never far from his mind. Just a week before his death he sent in his card regretting that because of ill health he could not attend this meeting, and added “But thank you for keeping me informed about CLR activities—it’s always a pleasure to hear.”

The main currents of Louis’ life are so familiar to us all that they only need to be recalled very briefly: born on March 1, 1899, in rural Greenwood County, South Carolina; attending Wofford College in nearby Spartanburg, where he majored in chemistry; interrupting his college career for a year of officer training at Plattsburgh in connection with World War I; returning to Spartanburg to take his degree; flying the mail in a dilapidated second-hand airplane—which entailed several crash landings in freshly plowed fields (he always maintained that the critical issue was whether you landed across or along the furrows); entering journalism as a newspaper reporter and editor of the local paper (where his activities in exposing corruption in some high places once got him shot at by the Ku Klux Klan); and a term as local deputy sheriff. All that preceded graduate work at Chapel Hill where he took his doctorate in 1926 and was immediately appointed an assistant professor of English at the University of North Carolina. After a year as a Guggenheim Fellow in Europe, he became in 1931

a visiting scholar at the newly opened Huntington Library in Pasadena, inaugurating sixteen years of brilliant research, organization and publication there, punctuated by teaching appointments at Michigan, Minnesota, and Washington and, nearer home, at Pomona, Cal Tech, and UCLA.

In 1948 Louis was called to Washington to succeed Joseph Quincy Adams as director of the Folger Library, and for the next twenty years, as we all know so well, his influence on literary scholarship was profound, including, as tangible evidence, the writing or editing of nearly sixty books not counting numerous editions of Shakespeare (a special love) and other playwrights, and countless articles. After twenty years of service at the Folger, he formally retired, but he continued to serve on innumerable boards, academic senates, and professional societies in Washington and abroad. Through it all, his deep interest and participation in a wide spectrum of libraries and librarianship remained a constant and dominating interest.

I would like to offer the following Resolution:

We of the Council on Library Resources, through this resolution, express our deep gratitude to Louis Booker Wright for his critical contributions to the shape, the purposes, and the daily work of the Council through its entire life, dating from the very moment of its conception, and, in a formal sense, for his service as Vice Chairman through the twenty-seven years of its existence. But even more, we tender our profound appreciation for the opportunity that he brought to us all to work with a colleague of the highest intellectual excellence and, most of all, with a spirit ennobling and inspiring for all of us.

Introduction

Highlights of the Council's 28th year and descriptions of active projects are included in the body of this report. Since the past is taken care of, we want to consider the future in these introductory pages. We do so with some hesitation because the funds for what we aspire to do are not in hand and it is by no means certain that they ever will be. But by definition, CLR is a risk-taking organization, so we will talk about the future "as if."

The Council, along with many other organizations, concerns itself with ways to improve all aspects of the process of putting recorded information to effective use, especially in the context of the needs and expectations of users of research libraries and members of the higher education community. This is a simply stated but most difficult undertaking, in part because of unprecedented volatility in the character of library services and information systems, and in part because there is no cohesive or even representative voice of the users.

The difficulty is surpassed only by the importance of the matter. In discussions and meetings with librarians, university officers, publishers, and others, the need has been forcefully expressed for more facts and better analytical studies concerning the generation, distribution, and use of information; the processes and quality of publication in all formats; legal, organizational, and economic issues implicit in changes under way; and, most of all, the future nature of libraries themselves.

Based on this exploratory work, we are convinced that there is a great gap between our understanding of the characteristics and use of information and the requirements of the "information society" that are now being shaped by many forces and interests. Further, it seems clear that as "information systems" provide more, they also grow increasingly complex and costly. Attention must be paid to topics that are now largely unexplored and a way must be found to articulate better the requirements of individual scholars and the long-term interests of universities and the broader public. Too little is known about such matters as the relationship between information availability and economic progress, the implications for society of constraints on access to information, the social role and functions of library and other information agencies, the quality and validity of information maintained in computer-based systems, or the relationship between format and usefulness. Information, in all of its forms, is the product of much human effort, but too little thought is given to the ways that product is used.

CLR has long included a research component in most of its continuing programs, but by and large the work has been closely linked to specific program needs. It is evident that the range of important issues is expanding rapidly, well beyond the limits of the Council's own capabilities. Many of those same issues also interest organizations and individuals other than libraries and librarians.

Looking to the immediate future, CLR hopes to establish a much-expanded research capacity, independent from development activities in established program areas. This new undertaking should promote productive new links between the Council and other organizations—universities, publishers, computer and other technology-based groups, library organizations, and, perhaps most important, the academic disciplines—that have program interests that complement our own.

The form, procedures, and agenda of this new research enterprise will be developed during the next year and we hope work on a number of topics will be under way by year's end. It is already certain that we are not considering a concentration of research activity in one place. Rather, the intent is to encourage interested and skilled people from several universities and many disciplines to undertake work along lines they themselves determine in the context of the set of topics chosen initially for the research agenda. We will look for ways to encourage participants to coordinate their work, provide for mutual support and critical evaluation, and, over time, develop a sense of cohesion in a common cause. We hope the Council's 29th Annual Report will carry the message that aspiration has been converted to reality.

Warren J. Haas

Program Review

Each year the Council on Library Resources mails its annual report to about 5,000 individuals and organizations who have an interest in what CLR does. More often than not, these readers from many countries are not only interested, but they share with us, and we with them, the responsibility for finding better ways to assemble, organize, preserve, and promote the use of publications and information in all forms, by all people, everywhere. With an aspiration of this magnitude, help from many individuals is essential and, each year, we are pleased to report that so many do help that it is unrealistic to consider acknowledging them individually. Once again, we begin our report with warm thanks, spread widely.

In the real world, money helps as well. Here, we have a relatively small number of generous foundations that provide the funds to keep us operating. We try to use these funds with great care, simply because they represent much of the risk capital that is available to address the common concerns of academic and research libraries. On behalf of the thousands who help CLR and the millions who teach and learn and use libraries, we want to acknowledge the financial support of the National Endowment for the Humanities and nine private foundations: the Carnegie Corporation of New York, the Exxon Education Foundation, The Ford Foundation, Pew Memorial Trust, The William R. and Flora Hewlett Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, The Rockefeller Foundation, and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation.

The reports on the primary areas of activity during 1983/84 follow. Together, they give some sense of the Council during the past year.

Library Resources, Preservation, and Access

There are several Council activities that aim to enhance, preserve, and extend access to the library collections that are the primary resources for teaching and research in this country.

The Association of Research Libraries was funded to produce a manual that will enable research libraries to enter assessment data about their collections into the online inventory of national collections developed originally for members of the Research Libraries Group. The manual, completed in January 1984, now is being tested in a few research libraries, and the methodology should be generally available by early 1985. The project provides a way to assemble information in a consistent way about distinctive collections and will serve as a foundation for many projected cooperative collection development, preservation, and resource sharing programs.

The Information Delivery Services program seeks to improve access to information and library materials. It was originally conceived because of the growing concern that the success of online bibliographic systems was creating new frustrations for users. Technology has greatly enhanced the means of identifying and locating information about information, but without a corresponding change in the way materials actually are delivered to those who need them. Several projects were funded to shed light on aspects of this general problem.

A study of current document delivery activities in the U.S. was completed in October 1983. The authors concluded that, while changes toward electronic delivery systems are inevitable in the future, the transition is taking place very slowly in research and academic libraries. Selected technologies were studied to determine their applications in extending and preserving collections. In other efforts, representatives of 14 libraries engaged in telefacsimile transmission projects agreed on a standard format for data collection in order to learn more about both costs and performance of telefacsimile systems. Information Systems Consultants Inc. was commissioned to review the potentially useful applications of video and digital disk technologies for information storage and retrieval and for preservation purposes.

The quality of databases and their usefulness to library users was another subject for research, and this general topic continues to be the focus of many discussions. Given the centrality of the matter, relatively little is known about how information

is generated, assembled, and used. Similarly, in conjunction with the Economics Seminar (see p. 21), a contract was awarded to examine the costs and benefits of library cooperation. As interdependence is more and more acknowledged as a necessity, questions arise concerning the economic implications for libraries and the methods for calculating benefits of resource sharing programs.

Traditionally, access and preservation have been separate elements on the Council's agenda, but there is a growing understanding that the two topics are but sides of the same coin. In the area of preservation, major strides have been made. Participants at an October 1983 CLR Forum on the topic of library resources and their preservation urged moving from planning to action, and CLR agreed to produce a paper outlining the necessary steps for a strategy to preserve the nation's intellectual heritage. A small working group, including Margaret Child, Smithsonian Institution, Harold Billings, University of Texas at Austin, and David Stam, New York Public Library, worked with CLR staff on the paper that became the basis for discussions at meetings of the Association of American Universities, the American Council of Learned Societies, and the Association of Research Libraries in the spring of 1984. All of these groups support continued action to develop a functioning preservation program.

In June 1984, the Exxon Education Foundation announced its intention to make available \$1.2 million for a regional preservation facility that will be equipped to do large-scale preservation work. Additional funds from the Foundation have been awarded to the Council for research on preservation-related topics, for national coordination and planning, and for beginning the task of educating the public about the magnitude of the problems and possible solutions.

Resolution of the "preservation problem" will require concentrated effort by many libraries over a long period of time. The cost and work will be best justified when the technology used to capture the content of deteriorating collections also can be used to extend access to these same materials to the scholarly community.

The following projects to enhance, preserve, and extend access to library resources were supported during the past year:

American Library Association

To partially fund expenses of speakers for a series of conferences on the preservation of library materials, sponsored by the Resources and Technical Services Division of ALA in cooperation with the Library of Congress.

Association of Research Libraries

To develop a procedural manual and training programs for bibliographers applying the Research Libraries Group collections conspectus in the ARL National Inventory of Research Collections Project.

Carleton College

To enable Ann Niles to produce a guide to microform collections not otherwise indexed. *An Index to Microform Collections* (Westport, Conn., Meckler Publishing) was published in the summer of 1984.

Council of National Library and Information Associations, Inc.

To provide support for the National Information Standards Organization (formerly American National Standards Institute Committee Z39), especially for work related to book paper quality.

Duke University

To collect information on the construction of Byzantine bindings and to make comparisons with other early bookbinding practices.

Information Systems Consultants Inc.

To study current interlibrary loan and document delivery activity and recommend topics for additional analysis. *Document Delivery in the United States* was published by the Council in 1983.

Information Systems Consultants Inc.

For a report on videodisk and optical digital disk technologies and their potential for library applications.

Library of Congress

To partially support costs incurred by participants in the Center for the Book's Symposium on the Public Lending Right, held September 29, 1983.

Ellis Mount

For certain costs incurred in gathering material for the second edition of his *University Science and Engineering Libraries* (Westport, Conn., Greenwood Press, 1975).

Syracuse University

To enable Mona Farid and Eileen Snyder to investigate the information-seeking behavior of students enrolled in Ph.D. programs.

Tantalus Inc.

To identify the costs, effects, and benefits of library consortium membership for library processes and services. (Funding shared with the Economics Seminar.)

University of California, Los Angeles

To enable Christine Borgman and Donald Case to conduct a feasibility study to assess the need for a "consumer's guide" to databases.

University of Hawaii at Manoa

Toward conference costs for a November 1983 seminar to provide librarians, publishers, writers, and booksellers with information on issues and problems of publishing for small markets in Hawaii and the Pacific Islands.

University of Minnesota

To enable M. J. Dustin and Anita Anker, Minnesota Interlibrary Telecommunication Exchange (MINITEX), to analyze network activity and develop a document delivery model.

Bibliographic Services

The Council's Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP) seeks to develop and employ a nationally acceptable strategy for acquiring and sharing bibliographic control over resources available to users of the nation's libraries. By working with producers of bibliographic records and encouraging cooperative activities, the BSDP pursues its principal goals: the provision of effective bibliographic services for all who need them, the improvement of bibliographic products, and the stabilization of costs of bibliographic processes in individual libraries.¹

A change in the focus of BSDP activity has occurred during the past year. In earlier years, the program provided a number of large and small grants, but during 1983/84 there was only one large grant and many smaller ones. Increasingly, the program has become a focus of and a means for encouraging communication among many who share similar interests.

One of the initial BSDP projects in early 1979 was to organize a meeting to discuss ways to approach a particularly thorny problem: linking computer systems. The meeting resulted in a series of extensive projects that are just now nearing completion and showing promise of resolving some of the issues identified at that time. As other issues needed attention, a similar strategy was followed: a meeting of invited experts and interested parties usually resulted in a set of recommendations and, as often as not, stimulated another cycle of projects and activities—some with Council funding and some without, but all aimed at resolving the problems under discussion.

The focused meeting strategy for dealing with pressing issues has produced other desirable outcomes, including improved communication among people with similar but only loosely related professional interests. The importance of the BSDP role in facilitating communication was recognized early, but its full effectiveness as an operating strategy has now become apparent. Encouraging effective communication will continue to be as important as any other single aspect of the program.

During 1983/84, the BSDP celebrated its fifth year of operation. Originally, the program was envisioned as a five-year effort, but because progress was slower than anticipated in some areas and additional work was identified in others, the Council sought and received approval from funding sources to extend the budgeted life of the BSDP by two years. Further, it is likely that there will still be work to be done

1. Members of the BSDP Program Committee are listed on p. 33.

beyond that date. Because a fifth year marks a chronological milestone, a review of the program was conducted, and a comprehensive report is available from the Council.

A formal review meeting held in December 1983 helped provide directions for further work. The strongest recommendation was that the Council continue its efforts to assure the development and implementation of linkages between the shared cataloging services. A second recommendation was that the BSDP continue and, if possible, expand its communication role. Since that time, the BSDP has hosted three meetings and planned two others, two of which were concerned with implementing links between the shared cataloging services and several other organizations.

Other meetings were devoted to online catalog issues. In September 1983, in Baltimore, online catalog designers discussed a number of system design problems. As a direct outgrowth of that meeting, another was held in March 1984 at OCLC headquarters in Dublin, Ohio, on command languages and screen displays for online catalogs.

Much effort also went into evaluating proposals for work designed to further program objectives. Support was provided to the Association of American Publishers for development of a standard for coding manuscripts in machine-readable form. It is anticipated that the standard will be proposed formally some time in 1985. The publishing community is interested in the standard and its application for production and, possibly, distribution purposes. The library community is interested in the codes as a means to capture bibliographic information from the original piece. In addition, other information might become part of the bibliographic record if properly encoded and made available, including tables of contents, index data, and abstracts and summaries, etc.

BSDP interest in the development and refinement of online catalogs continued to be expressed through a series of grants during 1983/84. Northwestern University is developing ways to train users of online catalogs, and to evaluate the effectiveness of that training. A grant to New York University assists efforts to determine how effectively the online catalog is being used, and Columbia University is evaluating the impact on all public services when an online catalog is introduced. OCLC and Forest Press, publisher of the Dewey Decimal Classification, are engaged in a joint project to determine whether that classification system and its supporting textual material might be used to enhance subject searching in an online catalog.

The University of California Systemwide Administration, Division of Library Automation, was funded to produce a computer terminal driven by packet radio signals as distinct from signals received via computer cabling. A terminal capable of supporting bibliographic processes was demonstrated at the meetings of the Association of Research Libraries and at the Seattle conference of the Association of College and Research Libraries. Additional work on the project is being supported by the commercial sector.

Jutta Reed-Scott and two collaborators have completed a report on retrospective conversion of bibliographic records to machine-readable form. In it, the authors assess the status of conversion projects and recommend a strategy for establishing a national effort. Two meetings are planned for the summer of 1984 to review the document and evaluate the recommendations.

Also of interest is the impending test and implementation of telecommunication links between the computers of the Library of Congress, the Research Libraries Group, and the Washington Library Network, within the BSDP's Linked Systems Project (LSP).² The project is intended to provide the technical capability to link large bibliographic databases. In order to provide information to potential users of the telecommunication protocols, interested libraries, commercial vendors, and shared cataloging services were included in a January 1984 meeting in San Francisco. OCLC has been involved in the several parts of the work as an observer, and at that meeting agreed to use and to further evaluate the LSP telecommunication protocols. The first planned implementation of the links is the exchange of authorities records.³ A grant has been made to the three LSP participants for planning for additional applications.

The following BSDP projects were active during the past year:

Association of American Publishers

To develop a standard set of codes for identifying various portions of manuscripts in electronic form, building on past work by the Graphic Communications Association, the American National Standards Institute, and the International Standards Organization.

Association of Research Libraries

To enable ARL and the National Federation of Abstracting and Indexing Services to enrich records in the CONSER database by adding information on coverage of serial titles by many abstracting and indexing services.

Association of Research Libraries

To partially fund a project to improve bibliographic access to publications in large microform collections by encouraging the addition of records for those items to the databases of the shared cataloging services.

Columbia University

For a study to measure the impact of online public access catalog implementation on all aspects of public services at the Columbia University Libraries.

C. Donald Cook, University of Toronto

To assess the extent of uniformity of application, during 1981, of AACR2 headings for corporate bodies, by four national libraries: the National Library of Australia, the British Library, the National Library of Canada, and the Library of Congress.

Council of National Library and Information Associations, Inc.

To provide support for the National Information Standards Organization (formerly American National Standards Institute Committee Z39), with emphasis on work related to holdings information and telecommunication protocols.

2. LSP participants are listed on p. 33.

3. For background, see Council on Library Resources *Annual Report XXVII*. Members of the Task Force on a Name Authority File Service are listed on p. 33.

Forest Press

In conjunction with the OCLC Online Computer Library Center, to explore the use of the Dewey Decimal Classification as a subject access enhancement for online catalogs.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

For consultative assistance in modifying the MINISIS management and information retrieval system software at Canada's International Development Research Center to support Universal MARC (UNIMARC), the standard communications format for bibliographic records adopted by IFLA. The product will enable many institutions in developing countries to process UNIMARC records.

J. Matthews & Associates

To enable Joseph Matthews and Gary Lawrence (University of California System-wide Administration) to analyze data gathered in the Online Public Access Catalog Evaluation Project.

Library of Congress

To cover travel and per diem costs incurred by Library of Congress personnel while working on the Linked Systems Project.

Library of Congress

To complete design work required for programming related to the Standard Network Interconnection.

Library of Congress

To develop three separate plans for coordinated intersite testing of the network, transport, and session layer protocols for the Standard Network Interconnection.

Linked Systems Project

Participants: The Library of Congress, the Research Libraries Group, and the Washington Library Network.

To design, develop, test, and implement a standardized telecommunication link, or Standard Network Interconnection, to make possible exchanges of data, initially between the LC, RLG, and WLN computer systems and ultimately between any pair of computer systems.

To implement the exchange of authority records, using the Standard Network Interconnection.

To analyze requirements and develop additional functional specifications for the online exchange of bibliographic records and related information, using communication links developed in the Linked Systems Project.

New York University

To evaluate the effectiveness of the library's new online catalog by determining actual results of searches and relating the results to users' stated levels of satisfaction.

Northwestern University

To develop a model teaching strategy for training online catalog users and to evaluate the effectiveness of the training through transaction log analysis.

OCLC Online Computer Library Center

In conjunction with Forest Press, to explore the use of the Dewey Decimal Classification as a subject access enhancement for online catalogs.

OHIONET

To develop and test an online subject thesaurus that links Library of Congress Subject Headings and Dewey Decimal and Library of Congress Classification numbers.

Pittsburgh Regional Library Center

To develop a standard method for identifying serial cancellations in online bibliographic databases.

The Research Libraries Group

To provide funding for a task force to plan to improve scholarly access to machine-readable data files by integrating records for those files into the Research Libraries Information Network.

Rutgers University

To design and establish a file of records for machine-readable texts in the humanities, to be entered into the Research Libraries Information Network.

Stanford University

To investigate end-user searching of bibliographic databases, comparing the effectiveness and costs of using the DIALOG command language versus the Institute for Scientific Information's Sci-Mate intermediary software.

Sarah E. Thomas, CLR Intern, University of Georgia

To analyze the serial holdings of the Center for Research Libraries to determine how easily CRL serials might be classified, to determine the distribution of institutions holding CRL serials, and to review in detail CRL holdings that also are held by the University of Georgia.

University of California Systemwide Administration

To investigate and report on the relationship of characteristics, capabilities, and features of online catalogs to their costs.

University of California Systemwide Administration

To assemble and build a demonstration packet radio terminal for use with online catalogs, and to demonstrate the system at the Third National Conference of the Association of College and Research Libraries, April 1984, and at the Association of Research Libraries meeting, April 1984.

University of Kentucky Research Foundation

To enable Lois M. Chan to revise her text, *Library of Congress Subject Headings: Principles and Application*, and to add material on changes influenced by AACR2 and a study of LC subject headings in online public access catalogs.

University of Michigan

To enable Victor Rosenberg to create microcomputer software to produce and maintain bibliographies, using the American National Standards Institute standards for bibliographic references. The software expedites the use of records from databases of several cataloging services.

Management

The management of libraries has long been a topic of great interest to the Council. During the year, support continued for specific activities of the Office of Management Studies of the Association of Research Libraries, and several grants were made to individuals for research and analytical studies on a variety of management issues. The most extensive new project is a CLR-administered study of the costs and funding of research libraries.

With financial support from the Lilly Endowment, CLR established an Economics Seminar in January 1984. The general goals of the program are to acquire and analyze library cost data that may be used to improve forecasting of library budgetary requirements during a time of economic and technological change. Lack of information about the expected magnitude and characteristics of library costs in the future is associated with a limited understanding of current library funding. While economic issues stimulated this new effort, library values and performance will be carefully considered when judging operating efficiency and benefits in relation to research, teaching, and scholarship.

The decisions now facing libraries regarding the use of computers and related technologies for internal operations, and the manner in which they provide computer-based information services for users, have important implications for performance and costs. From the viewpoints of scholars and students, as well as university officials and library directors, improvements in performance and efficiency will have important effects on determining future levels and sources of funding. Thus, the Council intends to investigate, from an economic perspective, new approaches for modifying library operations to improve the services and products provided to library patrons. The Seminar will help assemble and interpret the economic information required to guide research libraries in program planning and budgeting for the future.

Because the number of library consortia and service organizations has grown greatly during the last decade, a better understanding of the nature and future structure of multi-institutional interdependence is needed. Neither the continuing costs nor the economic and service benefits of library cooperatives have been assessed. The Council has contracted with Paul Kantor, a library management consultant, to explore the costs of library cooperation, using data obtained from representative members of regional and national library consortia.

The Council also has joined in sponsoring a cost-finding study undertaken by a task force of the Public Library Association. Cost concepts and definitions are being developed as guidelines for a workbook that will be used for specifying operating costs in a standardized way. The goal is to help improve analyses of public library functions.

The first Economics Seminar was held on March 6, 1984. Twelve university officials, research librarians, and economists participated in general discussions of library economics.¹ They also reviewed a proposal from Vanderbilt University to identify and measure the costs of staff, space, equipment, library materials, and other cost components related to library services and products. The seminar participants encouraged a detailed analysis of costs in several large research libraries, as well as an extensive study of the operating costs of all ARL member libraries. The ARL Committee on Statistics has undertaken the study of operating costs. The second Economics Seminar is scheduled for the fall of 1984.

The following management and economics projects were active during the year:

American Library Association

For partial support of a Public Library Association Cost Analysis Task Force project to develop a manual that defines cost concepts and provides methods of collecting and analyzing cost data for public libraries.

Association of Academic Health Sciences Library Directors

For partial funding of a joint AAHSLD/Medical Library Association project to produce guidelines for academic health sciences center libraries.

Association of Research Libraries

For support of the Academic Library Program of the Office of Management Studies to assist self-study, training, and organizational change efforts. This five-year grant ended September 30, 1983.

Association of Research Libraries

To enable the Office of Management Studies to test a collection use study manual at four member libraries of the Cooperative College Library Center, Atlanta: Atlanta College of Art, Dillard University, Tougaloo College, and Tuskegee Institute.

College Library Program

To improve undergraduate education by providing assistance to individual libraries for designing programs to support instruction. Originally funded in 1969 by CLR and the National Endowment for the Humanities, this program ended in 1984.

Malcolm Getz, Vanderbilt University

To design a data collection protocol for obtaining library cost and expenditure data, and to produce a state-of-the-art essay on the literature of library economics.

1. Participants are listed on p. 35.

Tantalus Inc.

To identify the costs and benefits of library consortium membership, and the effects on library processes and services. The Information Delivery Services program provides half of the cost of this study.

University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

To enable William Gray Potter to study collection overlap and diversity in 20 Illinois academic libraries that use the Library Computer System, a shared circulation system.

University of Michigan

To examine attitudes of faculty in selected disciplines concerning shelving books in storage facilities, and to test the influence of enhanced access and delivery services on those attitudes.

Whittier College

To cover direct travel and accommodation costs for five Earlham College faculty invited to conduct a bibliographic instruction workshop at Whittier College.

Professional Education and Training

The Council's Professional Education program assists librarians, library schools, and students in research librarianship.¹ Activity continued at a high level during the fourth year of the PETREL program. The University of Michigan continues to make special recruiting efforts for students from the liberal arts colleges with scientific, analytic, and quantitative backgrounds, and to provide an expanded curriculum in research librarianship. The Council's funding, which was scheduled for three years in decreasing amounts, has been supplemented by scholarships provided by the H. W. Wilson Foundation. The UCLA Senior Fellows Program, in its second year, brought 16 top-level managers and library educators to the campus for an intensive academic session in August 1983, followed by a year-long research project undertaken by each. At the two-year mark, a grant was made to UCLA to create a professional profile of the Senior Fellows in the first two classes, both to measure the success of the program and to learn more about the characteristics of leaders in research libraries.²

A central objective of the PETREL program, to promote more productive communication between library educators and practitioners, is reflected in the Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research program, which is an effort to stimulate team research. In the October 1983 cycle, seventeen proposals were received, four of which were funded. In the April 1984 cycle, twenty-one proposals were received and seven were funded. These small grants (the maximum is \$3,000) are designed to encourage research projects that aid in solving practical library problems. The research reports that have been produced are of high quality and testify to the worth of this program. The hope is to encourage even more proposals so that as many as 30 might be funded annually.

A new way to bring educators and practitioners together is demonstrated by the Library Educators' Institute. The Association of Research Libraries received a CLR grant to design a three-week program for faculty members who specialize in academic/research librarianship, to be held in the summer of 1984. The institute introduces participants to current issues related to the library's role in higher education and features study of aspects of research library operations.

1. Members of the PETREL Program Committee are listed on p. 34.

2. Senior Fellows are listed on p. 34.

The tenth class of CLR Academic Library Management Interns, selected early in 1984, includes six librarians chosen from an applicant pool of 49. This program is a continuing effort to identify and train well-qualified individuals for senior management posts.

While these activities have assisted many talented individuals, there is still no clear indication of fundamental change and substantial improvement in many aspects of professional education. To stimulate review and innovation, and with the advice of the PETREL advisory committee, CLR in 1984 launched a new program aimed at improving professional education at a larger number of schools. Universities, libraries, and graduate library schools are invited to request support for incremental costs incurred in planning new programs or improvements in existing programs at the basic professional level or in formal continuing professional education. The planning grants of up to \$5,000 each are made on evidence of institutional commitment as well as on a description of objectives. Plans will be judged competitively for a limited number of implementation grants during 1984 and 1985.

Eight planning grants were awarded in the first review. It is too early to predict the influence this program will have, but the need to draw university officials into the discussion of their expectations for librarians and the educational requirements of the profession seems clear.

As another way to enhance professional education, CLR proposed to the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation the creation of research library internships, and in June 1984, Mellon granted \$500,000 to be used over a three-year period for this purpose. The intent is to offer support on a competitive basis to research libraries to develop internships for recent library school graduates. A primary objective of the internships is to introduce newly employed librarians to the full range of research activity in the university and to the varying research methods and information requirements of individual disciplines.

The following professional education and training projects were active during the past year:

Association of Research Libraries

To enable the Office of Management Studies to design and operate an institute to extend library educators' understanding of research library issues and operations.

Atlanta University

To develop a plan to recruit and train science librarians at the master's degree level for careers in academic/research librarianship.

Nancy Bell, Johns Hopkins University

To partially support a conservation internship in the United Kingdom, and to publish comparative descriptions of library conservation practices.

Jovana Brown, Evergreen State College

To cover direct costs of studying the work of research units established by the Office of Scientific and Technical Information, Great Britain.

Case Western Reserve University

For partial support of a study of the place of information science in the university curriculum.

Kent State University

To explore several options for extending the MLS program.

Rutgers University

To develop a plan for recruiting and training scientists and engineers in research librarianship.

University of British Columbia School of Librarianship

For Frontiers Conference II: an invitational conference to evaluate changing technology and its impact on scholarly communication, research libraries, and education for librarianship and information science. Also, for summarizing and editing the proceedings of the conference, held in June 1983.

University of California, Los Angeles

To continue the Senior Fellows Program, which provides senior library administrators with opportunities for intensive specialized study in management and independent research.

University of California, Los Angeles

For a study of characteristics of research library leaders through analysis of the career paths of CLR Senior Fellows and comparison of the Fellows' career patterns with those of a control group.

University of Chicago

To conduct a systematic evaluation of the curriculum in the areas of library automation and information science at the University of Chicago Graduate Library School.

University of Denver

To assess the need among western academic/research librarians for a special certificate program in academic/research librarianship.

University of Michigan

To provide fellowship funding through spring 1985 for the School of Library Science's program to prepare specially recruited students for leadership roles in academic research libraries.

University of Oklahoma

To design a program for improving information resource management skills through interdisciplinary work in research methodology, evaluation techniques, interpersonal skills, information systems applications, and marketing.

University of Wisconsin, Madison

To develop a supplementary education program for librarians currently employed in research libraries, with the objective of increasing participants' ability to undertake research in cooperation with scholars from other disciplines.

*Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research Projects
1982-83 Grants*

Julia Gelfand and John King, University of California, Irvine

To study the effects of consolidation in a university library, including economies of scale and the preservation of services to multidisciplinary research units.

Kathleen Heim and Paula Watson, University of Illinois

To study the use of government documents in a large research library.

Terrence Brooks and John W. Forsy, Jr., University of Iowa

To evaluate the efficiency of eight forecasting methods for library circulation statistics and provide a forecasting method that can be performed with a desk calculator.

Cynthia Dobson, Paula Morrow, and Dilys Morris, Iowa State University

To investigate the impact of new physical facilities on job satisfaction and job performance.

Beth Shapiro and Philip Marcus, Michigan State University

To assess the success rates of library users in retrieving materials located in the main library.

George D'Elia, Andrea Hinding, and Cerise Oberman, University of Minnesota

To analyze and evaluate the document delivery service provided for faculty members in six academic units.

Ben-Ami Lipetz, State University of New York at Albany, and Peter Paulson, New York State Library

To measure the impact on users of the addition of online subject searching to the catalog of the New York State Library.

Robert Swisher and Rosemary Du Mont, University of Oklahoma, and Calvin Boyer, University of California, Irvine

To study the extent to which female academic/research librarians seek administrative positions.

Marcy Murphy, Indiana University, and Martha Bailey, Purdue University

To identify managerial competencies at four professional levels in research libraries.

Patricia Reeling, Daniel O'Connor, and Mary Fetzer, Rutgers University

For an investigation of the extent and nature of use of the government publications collection at the university library.

Thomas Martin and John Wyman, Syracuse University

To develop techniques to analyze searches in the library's online public catalog so that library staff can identify and test modifications to the system and to user documentation.

Anne LeClercq and Ernest Brewer, University of Tennessee

To develop a model for providing library resources and services to college-bound high school students.

Malcolm Getz and Douglas Phelps, Vanderbilt University

To investigate technical services costs in three university libraries.

Jordan Scepanski and Edwin Gleaves, Vanderbilt University

To investigate the information needs, habits, and attitudes of faculty members of the George Peabody College for Teachers, Vanderbilt University.

Ruth Patrick and Robert Booth, Wayne State University

To study the introduction of microcomputers in the university library.

Leonard Geddie, Elizabeth Dolan, and Alexis Jamieson, University of Western Ontario

To investigate the relative value of keyword search capabilities and authority control in an online catalog.

1983-84 Grants

Ruth Person, Catholic University, and George Charles Newman, State University College of New York at Buffalo

To study the selection process for university library directors.

Louis Martin and Jan Olsen, Cornell University

To compare the costs and delivery times of three different suppliers for interlibrary loan requests.

Kathleen Gunning, University of Houston, and Carolyn Frost, University of Michigan

To explore requirements for making subject access via Library of Congress subject headings more comprehensible to online catalog users.

Carolyn Snyder, George Whitbeck, and Stella Bentley, Indiana University

To study the costs of public services in research libraries.

Ronald Powell and Sheila Creth, University of Michigan

To survey the graduates of the university's library school to assess their present needs for job skills.

Karen Smith and Stuart Shapiro, State University of New York at Buffalo

To develop a diagnostic computerized system to direct users to reference sources in the government documents department.

Andrew Torok and Jitka Hurych, Northern Illinois University

To study online searching of bibliographic and numeric databases.

Marjorie Murfin, Ohio State University, and Charles Bunge, University of Wisconsin

To analyze survey data for an assessment of reference services.

Pamela Vance and Leon Montgomery, University of Pittsburgh

To investigate the demand for rapid document delivery service and, if needed, formulate a plan for implementation.

Virginia Bowden and Sharon Fought, University of Texas Health Science Center

To compare collections of recent (1977-83) nursing monographs in 15 academic health science center libraries in the Southwest.

Keith Miller and Jean Johnson, University of Wyoming

To study library resources and services required to meet the needs of nontraditional library users.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

To help outstanding individuals broaden their experience and enhance their management skills through nine-month internships at research libraries.³ The 1984–85 interns are:

Joseph J. Branin, University of Georgia Libraries, interning with Patricia Battin, vice president and university librarian, Columbia University.

Nicholas C. Burckel, University of Wisconsin, Parkside, interning with Martin Runkle, director, University of Chicago Library.

James Alan Cogswell, Princeton University, interning with Susan Martin, director of libraries, John Hopkins University.

Carolyn Louise Harris, Columbia University Libraries, interning with David Bishop, director of libraries, University of Georgia.

Arlyne A. Jackson, Dewey Library, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, interning with Herbert Johnson, director of libraries, Emory University.

Paul Douglas Metz, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, interning with John McGowan, university librarian, Northwestern University.

3. Members of the selection committee are listed on p. 34.

Special Programs

In addition to the continuing programs that shape much CLR activity, there are always a few specific matters that need attention for limited periods of time or activities that CLR undertakes in cooperation with other organizations. During 1983/84, the international field and public archives received special attention and, in cooperation with the Association of American Universities and the American Council of Learned Societies, CLR sponsored Forum II.

International Library Activity

CLR has assisted the organizational and program development of the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions for many years. The resulting growth in size and influence of IFLA has made it the central international organization concerned with all aspects of library and information service in all parts of the world. The organization has two quite distinct categories of primary activities. One stems from professional interests and concerns expressed through individual delegates and attended to in the professional structure of the organization. The other involves a small set of topical issues (the so-called core programs) that can be most usefully addressed by especially developed, targeted activity. The IFLA Office for Universal Bibliographic Control, housed at the British Library, is an example. This aspect of IFLA work is of primary importance to major research libraries and, as a result of IFLA planning committee deliberations in 1983, several additions to core programs were recommended, including conservation and preservation, transborder data flow and related problems of data exchange, and further development of international MARC.

To expedite development of the new core programs, CLR has funded the position of Service Program Manager for a two-year period. This individual will work closely with the IFLA Executive Board and the Conference of Directors of National Libraries. By the end of the grant period, IFLA plans to have developed the operating base and long-term funding for the new programs.

Records of Government

A second special program concerns the records of government. Public archives, whether municipal, state, or federal, are an essential ingredient of the workings of every society. The problems facing archives, ranging from organizing, storing, and

preserving the sheer quantity of material that comes to them to dealing with increasing quantities of computer-stored information, are almost overwhelming. Ways must be found to recast the management of archival organizations and to employ computer and text storage technology in cost-effective ways. But most of all, the expectations of the public for the contents of and access to these public records need to be understood and articulated as a base for planning and action. CLR, with the American Council of Learned Societies and the Social Science Research Council, is sponsoring the work of a Committee on the Records of Government, chaired by Ernest R. May.¹ The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, The Rockefeller Foundation, and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation have joined the Council in funding the study. The Committee has met with many individuals and organizations concerned with all aspects of the subject and will prepare a draft of its report during the fall of 1984 for review. The final report will be completed and distributed early in 1985.

Forum II

The transformation of research libraries that now is under way will affect library operations, services, organization, and costs. Librarians, faculty members, and university administrative officers all have a stake in the library future and will be affected by the form it takes.

The Council is making a special effort to bring all interested parties into discussions on changes in the scholarly communication process. With the American Council of Learned Societies and the Association of American Universities, CLR has begun a series of Forums on major issues. Forum II, held in October 1983, concentrated on national and regional aspects of collecting and preserving library materials. Thirty-one participants from libraries, university faculties and administrations, publishing, and foundations met and considered a number of issues identified in a series of preliminary papers and during Forum I, held a year earlier.

The conclusions reached during the Forum helped shape much CLR activity concerning preservation during the ensuing year. That work is reviewed elsewhere in this report. In November 1983, reports on Forum I and Forum II were published and distributed. It is anticipated that additional Forums on other topics will be held during the next few years.

On a related matter, CLR has worked with the American Council of Learned Societies to help establish an Office of Scholarly Communication. The projected office, which was described to and endorsed by Forum II participants, will assemble information about scholarly production and publishing for use by the 44 ACLS constituent societies, explore the effect of technology on scholarly work and the influence of computers on the substance of scholarly inquiry, and seek to promote improved communication among groups concerned with various aspects of the system of scholarly communication.

The following special projects were active during the past year:

1. Members of the committee are listed on p. 35.

American Library Association

To help support initial planning efforts for the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions conference to be held in Chicago in 1985.

Forums

Sponsored by CLR, the Association of American Universities, and the American Council of Learned Societies, the Forums bring together individuals concerned with scholarly communication, considering libraries as part of the system that includes research and scholarship, book and journal publishing, obligations and concerns of university administrators, the needs of scholarly disciplines, and the supportive guidance of foundations. Forum II, held in October 1983, was devoted to "National and Regional Aspects of Collecting and Preserving Research Library Materials."

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

To help plan new core programs and establish a management structure.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

To support a five-year review of the International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions and the consultative services of the UBC Director in helping to establish national bibliographic structures for certain developing countries.

Records of Government

Sponsored by CLR, the American Council of Learned Societies, and the Social Science Research Council, the Committee on the Records of Government is conducting an 18-month inquiry (July 1983–December 1984) into issues surrounding the creation and preservation of government records.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

For partial support for an International Conference on Research Library Cooperation, to be held October 1–3, 1984.

Research Panel

To cover the expenses of a research panel to consult with CLR staff on the topics, personnel, and methodology for an expanded CLR-supported research effort relative to library service and information systems.

Program Committees, Task Forces, And Project Participants

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM PROGRAM COMMITTEE

Henriette Avram
Library of Congress

Rowland Brown
OCLC, Inc.

Joan Gotwals
University of Pennsylvania

James Govan
University of North Carolina

Carol Ishimoto
Harvard University

Frederick Kilgour
OCLC, Inc.

Richard McCoy
The Research Libraries Group

Roderick Swartz
Washington State Library

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM TASK FORCE ON A NAME AUTHORITY FILE SERVICE

Raymond DeBuse
Washington Library Network

Joan Gotwals
University of Pennsylvania

Dorothy Gregor
University of California, Berkeley

Tina Kass
The Research Libraries Group

Lillian Kozuma
National Library of Medicine

Penny Mattern
OCLC, Inc.

Lucia Rather
Library of Congress

Helen Schmierer
University of Chicago

Ruth Shipp
Seattle Public Library

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM LINKED SYSTEMS PROJECT

Library of Congress
Principal Investigator and
Program Officer:
Project Directors:

Henriette Avram
Sally McCallum, Authorities
Ray Denenberg, Telecommunications

The Research Libraries Group
Principal Investigator:
Project Directors:

Richard McCoy
Tina Kass, Authorities
Wayne Davison, Telecommunications

Washington Library Network
Principal Investigator:
Project Directors:

Roderick Swartz
Raymond DeBuse, Authorities
Tom Brown, Telecommunications

PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING FOR RESEARCH
LIBRARIANSHIP
PROGRAM COMMITTEE

John McDonald, Chair
University of Connecticut
Russell Bidlack
University of Michigan
Margot McBurney
Queen's University
Rutherford Rogers
Yale University
Robert Vosper
University of California, Los Angeles

PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING FOR RESEARCH
LIBRARIANSHIP
SENIOR FELLOWS PROGRAM PARTICIPANTS

Class of 1983-84

Joseph Dagnese <i>Purdue University</i>	Robert Miller <i>Notre Dame University</i>
Laurent-G. Denis <i>University of Toronto</i>	Paul Mosher <i>Stanford University</i>
Kaye Gapen <i>University of Alabama</i>	Ann Prentice <i>University of Tennessee</i>
Dorothy Gregor <i>University of California, Berkeley</i>	Frank Rodgers <i>University of Miami</i>
Frances Groen <i>McGill University</i>	Jordan Scepanski <i>Vanderbilt University</i>
Irene Hoadley <i>Texas A & M University</i>	Richard Talbot <i>University of Massachusetts</i>
David Laird <i>University of Arizona</i>	Clyde Walton <i>University of Colorado</i>
Margot McBurney <i>Queen's University</i>	Howard White <i>Drexel University</i>

ACADEMIC LIBRARY MANAGEMENT INTERN PROGRAM
1984-85 SELECTION COMMITTEE

Fred Cole, Chair
Former president, CLR
Millicent Abell
University of California, San Diego
Linda Beaupré
University of Texas at Austin
Charles Churchwell
Washington University
Duane Webster
*Association of Research Libraries
Office of Management Studies*

COMMITTEE ON THE RECORDS OF GOVERNMENT

Ernest May, Chair

Charles Warren Professor of History, Harvard University

Richard Bolling

*Professor of American Politics (O'Neill Chair), Boston College
(Member of Congress, 1948–1982)*

Philip Buchen

*Dewey, Ballantine, Busbby, Palmer & Wood
(Counsel to President Ford, 1974–1977)*

Joseph Califano, Jr.

*Dewey, Ballantine, Busbby, Palmer & Wood
(Secretary, Department of Health, Education & Welfare, 1977–1979)*

Phillip Hughes

*Undersecretary, Smithsonian Institution
(Office of Management and Budget, 1949–1969)*

Edward Levi

*University of Chicago
(Attorney-General of the United States, 1975–1977)*

Franklin Lindsay

ITEK Corporation (Chairman of the Board, 1975–)

SEMINAR ON THE ECONOMICS OF RESEARCH LIBRARIES

March 1984

David Breneman

Kalamazoo College

Richard De Gennaro

University of Pennsylvania

Billy Frye

University of Michigan

Malcolm Getz

Vanderbilt University

James Hyatt

*National Association of College and
University Business Officers*

Paul Kantor

Tantalus Inc.

William Massy

Stanford University

Richard Talbot

University of Massachusetts

Lawrence White

New York University

Publications Resulting From CLR-Supported Programs And Fellowships, 1983–1984

Part I. Programs

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Washington, D.C., Council on Library Resources, November 1983.

Part II. Fellowships

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**ACTIVE PROJECTS
FINANCIAL STATEMENTS**

Grants and Contracts Active in Fiscal 1984 (unaudited)

	Unpaid 6/30/83	FY 1984		Unpaid 6/30/84
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Academic Library Management Intern Program				
1983-84	\$ -0-	\$135,000 (577)	\$ 134,028	\$ 395
1984-85	-0-	162,000	800	161,200
American Library Association Chicago, Ill.				
1985 IFLA General Conference	-0-	15,000	15,000	-0-
Public Library Association Cost Analysis Task Force	-0-	4,000	4,000	-0-
Association of Academic Health Sciences Library Directors Washington, D.C.				
Guidelines for academic health sciences center libraries	-0-	18,000	-0-	18,000
Association of American Publishers Washington, D.C.				
Development of publishing industry standards and author guidelines in electronic manuscript preparation	-0-	50,000	25,000	25,000
Association of Research Libraries Washington, D.C.				
Academic Library Program	23,500	-0-	15,000	8,500
ARL microforms project	2,000	-0-	2,000	-0-
Collection assessment for small academic libraries	2,200	-0-	-0-	2,200
Dillard University New Orleans, La.	500	-0-	500	-0-
Tougaloo College Tougaloo, Miss.	500	-0-	500	-0-
Tuskegee Institute Tuskegee Institute, Ala.	500	-0-	500	-0-
CONSER abstracting and indexing coverage project	75,500	-0-	20,000	55,500
Institute for library educators	-0-	54,700	21,450	33,250
National inventory of research collections	46,855	-0-	43,500	3,355

	FY 1984			Unpaid 6/30/84
	Unpaid 6/30/83	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Atlanta University				
Atlanta, Ga.				
Training program for science librarians	-0-	4,000	4,000	-0-
Nancy J. Bell				
Baltimore, Md.				
Conservation internship in the United Kingdom	2,500	-0-	2,500	-0-
Carleton College				
Northfield, Minn.				
Index to microform collections	250	(525)	(525)	250
Case Western Reserve University				
Cleveland, Ohio				
University commission on information sciences	-0-	5,000	5,000	-0-
Columbia University				
New York, N.Y.				
Measuring the public services impact of an online catalog	-0-	19,200	8,000	11,200
C. Donald Cook				
Toronto, Canada				
Study of forms of AACR2 catalog headings used by national libraries	5,000	(4,899)	2,000 (1,899)	-0-
Cornell University				
Ithaca, N.Y.				
Comparison of document delivery services	-0-	2,995	2,995	-0-
Council of National Library and Information Associations				
Haverford, Penn.				
Support of American National Standards Committee Z39	7,500	-0-	-0-	7,500
Dartmouth College Library				
Hanover, N.H.				
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	919	(27)	892	-0-

	FY 1984			
	Unpaid 6/30/83	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/84
Duke University				
Durham, N.C.				
Research on Byzantine bindings	2,500	-0-	-0-	2,500
Earlham College				
Richmond, Ind.				
7th conference on bibliographic instruction	-0-	(141)	(141)	-0-
Forest Press				
Albany, N.Y.				
The Dewey Decimal Classification as an online searching tool for subject access	-0-	94,350	57,000	37,350
Investigation of the need for an Arabic edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification	2,070	-0-	2,070	-0-
Malcolm Getz				
Nashville, Tenn.				
Preparation of a survey of library economics literature	-0-	5,000	2,500	2,500
Indiana University				
Bloomington, Ind.				
Public services costs study	-0-	2,850	2,850	-0-
Information Systems				
Consultants, Inc.				
Document delivery survey	2,800	(938)	1,862	-0-
Study of videodisk and optical digital disk technologies	-0-	14,750	6,250	8,500
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions				
The Hague, Netherlands				
Implementing a UNIMARC/MINISIS interface	-0-	5,800	5,800	-0-
Planning IFLA core programs	-0-	114,000	47,000	67,000
Report on copyright and materials for the handicapped	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
Review of international standard bibliographic descriptions	2,500	-0-	2,500	-0-
Special projects	20,000	(20,000)	-0-	-0-

	FY 1984			
	Unpaid 6/30/83	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/84
J. Matthews and Associates				
Grass Valley, Calif.				
Detailed analysis of the CLR online catalog data	27,000	-0-	27,000	-0-
Kent State University				
Kent, Ohio				
Options for extending the library science program	-0-	5,000	5,000	-0-
Library of Congress				
Washington, D.C.				
Joint project for authorities implementation	149,485	-0-	100,000	49,485
Bibliographic Analysis— Linked Systems Project	3,120	-0-	-0-	3,120
Design work—Standard Network Interconnection	-0-	(424)	(424)	-0-
Symposium on the public lending right	-0-	5,000	5,000	-0-
Telenet connection for SNI development	-0-	(699)	(699)	-0-
Travel costs for the Linked Systems Project	3,755	-0-	2,274	1,481
Ellis Mount				
Teaneck, N.J.				
Revision of <i>University Science and Engineering Libraries</i>	750	-0-	750	-0-
National Library of Canada				
Ottawa, Canada				
CONSER/COM	-0-	(7,416)	(7,416)	-0-
New York University				
New York, N.Y.				
Study of user success with an online catalog	-0-	15,736	14,000	1,736
Northern Illinois University				
DeKalb, Ill.				
Identification and analysis of factors affecting end-user online searching	-0-	2,145	-0-	2,145

	FY 1984			
	Unpaid 6/30/83	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/84
Northwestern University				
Evanston, Ill.				
Development of a model for training online catalog users	42,000	-0-	15,000	27,000
Ohio State University Research Foundation				
Columbus, Ohio				
Survey of reference services	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
OHIONET				
Columbus, Ohio				
Subject thesaurus research for an online catalog	-0-	8,112	7,500	612
Ruth Person				
Washington, D.C.				
Study of the selection process for university librarians	-0-	3,000	1,000	2,000
Pittsburgh Regional Library Center				
Pittsburgh, Penn.				
Serials cancellation project	1,500	-0-	1,500	-0-
Research Foundation of the State of New York				
Albany, N.Y.				
Development of a computer- assisted documents reference capability	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
The Research Libraries Group, Inc.				
Stanford, Calif.				
International conference on research library cooperation	-0-	10,000	-0-	10,000
Joint project for authorities implementation	244,245	-0-	85,000	159,245
Bibliographic analysis— Linked Systems Project	11,470	-0-	-0-	11,470
Joint project for Standard Network Interconnection	197,500	-0-	158,000	39,500
Planning the integration of machine-readable data files into the Research Libraries Information Network	7,000	-0-	7,000	-0-

	FY 1984			
	Unpaid 6/30/83	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/84
Toward the formation of a nationwide authority file service (joint project with WLN and LC)	16,554	-0-	16,554	-0-
Rutgers University				
New Brunswick, N.J.				
Inventory of machine-readable texts in the humanities	12,253	-0-	9,453	2,800
Training program for research librarians in science and technology	-0-	4,846	-0-	4,846
Stanford University				
Stanford, Calif.				
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	-0-	(527)	(527)	-0-
Study of alternate approaches to end-user searching	-0-	24,300	20,000	4,300
Tantalus Inc.				
Cleveland, Ohio				
Study of the costs of consortium membership	-0-	23,500	15,000	8,500
Sarah E. Thomas				
Athens, Ga.				
Analysis of serial holdings of the Center for Research Libraries	-0-	1,000	1,000	-0-
University of British Columbia				
Vancouver, B.C.				
Frontiers Conference II— Changing Technology	8,000	679	8,679	-0-
University of California				
Berkeley, Calif.				
Analysis of data collected in the online catalog evaluation project	26,903	(763)	26,140	-0-
Demonstration of a packet radio terminal system	-0-	15,000	10,000	5,000
Analysis of the features and costs of online catalogs	5,500	-0-	5,500	-0-
Participant in joint project to evaluate online public access catalogs	1,000	-0-	1,000	-0-

	FY 1984			
	Unpaid 6/30/83	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/84
University of California				
Los Angeles, Calif.				
Feasibility study for a consumer's guide to databases for the researcher	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Frontiers conference	40,000	(16,866)	23,134	-0-
Professional profile of CLR senior fellows	-0-	3,843	3,843	-0-
Senior fellows program				
1982-83	56,593	(33,193)	23,400	-0-
1983-85	127,000	-0-	70,608	56,392
University of Chicago				
Chicago, Ill.				
Conference— <i>Publishing Today</i>	2,300	-0-	2,300	-0-
Curriculum evaluation in library automation and information science	-0-	5,000	-0-	5,000
Special program of advanced study in library management	128,000	(145,819)	(17,819)	-0-
University of Denver				
Denver, Colo.				
Needs assessment among academic/research librarians	-0-	5,000	5,000	-0-
University of Hawaii at Manoa				
Honolulu, Hawaii				
Seminar on publishing in Hawaii and the Pacific Islands	-0-	1,000	1,000	-0-
University of Houston				
Houston, Tex.				
Improvement of subject access to the <i>Library of Congress Subject Headings</i>	-0-	2,350	-0-	2,350
University of Illinois				
Champaign, Ill.				
Collection overlap and diversity in the LCS network in Illinois	6,500	-0-	3,180	3,320
University of Iowa				
Iowa City, Iowa				
Study of methods for predicting library circulation	-0-	(1,298)	(1,298)	-0-

	FY 1984			Unpaid 6/30/84
	Unpaid 6/30/83	Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
University of Kentucky				
Research Foundation				
Lexington, Ky.				
Second edition of <i>Library of</i>				
<i>Congress Subject Headings:</i>				
<i>Principles and Application</i>	2,360	-0-	-0-	2,360
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University of Michigan				
Ann Arbor, Mich.				
Basic professional education				
for research librarianship	179,585	-0-	44,469	135,116
Job skills assessment	-0-	1,300	-0-	1,300
Study of the relationship				
between bibliographic access				
to stored materials and				
faculty attitude and use	31,747	-0-	-0-	31,747
A system for creating and				
maintaining bibliographies	7,500	-0-	7,500	-0-
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University of Minnesota				
St. Paul, Minn.				
Development of a document				
delivery model	-0-	5,127	-0-	5,127
Analysis and evaluation of				
document delivery service	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
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University of Oklahoma				
Norman, Okla.				
Information resources management				
skills for academic librarians	-0-	5,000	5,000	-0-
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University of Pittsburgh				
Pittsburgh, Penn.				
Study of demand for rapid				
document delivery service	-0-	2,995	-0-	2,995
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University of Texas				
San Antonio, Tex.				
Comparative analysis of				
monographic collections in				
nursing	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
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University of Wisconsin-Madison				
Madison, Wis.				
Supplementary education program				
for academic and research librarians	-0-	3,945	3,945	-0-

	Unpaid 6/30/83	FY 1984		Unpaid 6/30/84
		Grants (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
University of Wyoming				
Laramie, Wyo.				
Study of non-traditional academic library users in Wyoming	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University				
Blacksburg, Va.				
Research on use of library materials	2,310	(2,143)	167	-0-
Washington Library Network				
Olympia, Wash.				
Joint project for authorities implementation	213,801	-0-	140,000	73,801
Bibliographic analysis— Linked Systems Project	6,887	-0-	-0-	6,887
Joint project for Standard Network Interconnection	247,500	-0-	165,000	82,500
Whittier College				
Whittier, Calif.				
Bibliographic Instruction Workshop	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
Totals	\$2,014,712	\$875,523 (236,255)	\$1,491,393 (30,748)	\$1,193,335

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 6, 1984

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying balance sheets and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balances, of functional expenses and of changes in cash and short-term investments present fairly the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1984 and 1983, the results of its operations for the year ended June 30, 1984 and the changes in its cash and short-term investments for the two years then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied. Our examinations of these statements were made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

Price Waterhouse
Washington, D.C

Balance Sheets

	<u>JUNE 30</u>	
	<u>1984</u>	<u>1983</u>
ASSETS		
Cash and short-term investments, including restricted amounts of \$1,492,363 and \$1,832,667, respectively	\$3,532,672	\$3,634,269
Grants receivable (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	900,000	750,000
Restricted	3,676,200	2,662,592
Prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>8,016</u>	<u>9,887</u>
Total assets	<u>\$8,116,888</u>	<u>\$7,056,748</u>
LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Deferred income (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	\$1,150,000	\$1,000,000
Restricted	4,211,136	2,544,785
Grants and contracts payable	1,193,335	2,014,712
Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	52,759	63,462
Federal excise taxes payable	<u>6,039</u>	<u>4,837</u>
Total liabilities	<u>6,613,269</u>	<u>5,627,796</u>
Unrestricted fund balance		
Appropriated	830,452	942,703
Unappropriated	<u>673,167</u>	<u>486,249</u>
Total fund balance	<u>1,503,619</u>	<u>1,428,952</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u>\$8,116,888</u>	<u>\$7,056,748</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balance

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1984

(With Comparative Totals for 1983)

	Unrestricted	Restricted	Total 1984	Total 1983*
Revenues (Note 2)				
Grants and contracts	\$ 450,000	\$983,648	\$1,433,648	\$ 998,995
Investment income	<u>301,965</u>	<u> </u>	<u>301,965</u>	<u>241,857</u>
Total revenues	<u>751,965</u>	<u>983,648</u>	<u>1,735,613</u>	<u>1,240,852</u>
Expenses (Note 2)				
Program services				
Resources, preservation and access	13,585	105,281	118,866	122,559
Bibliographic services	2,124	479,786	481,910	399,595
Management	31,561	45,048	76,609	33,862
Professional education and training	330,900	(25,616)	305,284	212,680
Special programs	<u>27,493</u>	<u>234,149</u>	<u>261,642</u>	<u>108,193</u>
Total program services	405,663	838,648	1,244,311	876,889
Administration and program support services	<u>271,635</u>	<u>145,000</u>	<u>416,635</u>	<u>375,077</u>
Total expenses	<u>677,298</u>	<u>983,648</u>	<u>1,660,946</u>	<u>1,251,966</u>
Excess (deficiency) of revenues over expenses	74,667		74,667	(11,114)
Fund balance, beginning of year	<u>1,428,952</u>	<u> </u>	<u>1,428,952</u>	<u>1,440,066</u>
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$1,503,619</u>	<u>\$ </u>	<u>\$1,503,619</u>	<u>\$1,428,952</u>

*Reclassified for comparative purposes.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

**STATEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES
FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1984**

(With Comparative Totals for 1983)

	Program Services						Administration and Program Support Services	Year ended June 30	
	Resources, Preservation and Access	Bibliographic Services	Management	Professional Education and Training	Special Programs	Total Program Services		1984	1983
Unrestricted									
Grants and contracts	\$ 1,000		\$ 18,000	\$ 297,000	\$ 5,296	\$ 321,296		\$ 321,296	\$ 26,000
Refunds and overappropriations	(2,808)	\$ (12,315)		(577)		(15,700)		(15,700)	(19,906)
Staff and travel	13,253	13,254	13,253	20,512	13,253	73,525	\$ 164,072	237,597	303,337
Advisory committees	1,995			13,369	6,050	21,414	1,556	22,970	17,485
Consultants			163		2,585	2,748	17,835	20,583	18,564
Office expenses	145	1,185	145	596	309	2,380	88,172	90,552	157,491
	<u>13,585</u>	<u>2,124</u>	<u>31,561</u>	<u>330,900</u>	<u>27,493</u>	<u>405,663</u>	<u>271,635</u>	<u>677,298</u>	<u>502,971</u>
Restricted									
Grants and contracts	24,877	233,498	20,750	126,648	148,454	554,227		554,227	531,380
Refunds and overappropriations	(938)	(2,439)		(197,178)	(20,000)	(220,555)		(220,555)	(166,149)
Staff and travel	67,254	152,174		26,349	44,803	290,580	56,806	347,386	237,931
Advisory committees	3,153	88,367	5,149	4,285	19,460	120,414		120,414	72,908
Consultants	6,506	2,180	18,775	12,054	39,261	78,776		78,776	28,088
Office expenses	4,429	6,006	374	2,226	2,171	15,206	88,194	103,400	44,837
	<u>105,281</u>	<u>479,786</u>	<u>45,048</u>	<u>(25,616)</u>	<u>234,149</u>	<u>838,648</u>	<u>145,000</u>	<u>983,648</u>	<u>748,995</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$ 118,866</u>	<u>\$ 481,910</u>	<u>\$ 76,609</u>	<u>\$ 305,284</u>	<u>\$ 261,642</u>	<u>\$ 1,244,311</u>	<u>\$ 416,635</u>	<u>\$ 1,660,946</u>	<u>\$ 1,251,966</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statements of Changes in Cash and Short-term Investments

	<u>Year ended June 30</u>	
	<u>1984</u>	<u>1983</u>
Sources (uses) of cash and short-term investments		
Excess (deficiency) of revenues over expenses	\$ 74,667	\$ (11,114)
Increase in deferred income	1,816,351	1,766,877
Decrease (increase) in prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>1,871</u>	<u>(4,226)</u>
	<u>1,892,889</u>	<u>1,751,537</u>
Uses of cash and short-term investments		
Increase in grants receivable	1,163,608	146,181
Decrease in grants and contracts payable	821,377	697,214
Decrease in federal excise taxes, accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	<u>9,501</u>	<u>25,139</u>
	<u>1,994,486</u>	<u>868,534</u>
(Decrease) increase in cash and short-term investments for the year	(101,597)	883,003
Cash and short-term investments, beginning of year	<u>3,634,269</u>	<u>2,751,266</u>
Cash and short-term investments, end of year	<u>\$3,532,672</u>	<u>\$3,634,269</u>

Notes to Financial Statements

JUNE 30, 1984 AND 1983

Note 1—Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a nonprofit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through several restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

The Council is a private operating foundation and is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3). It is, however, subject to a 2% excise tax on investment income under the provisions of the Revenue Act of 1978.

Note 2—Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

The Council's financial statements have been prepared on the accrual basis of accounting. The significant accounting policies followed in the preparation of the financial statements are described below.

Grants

Grants are recorded as receivables and deferred revenue at such time as the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Restricted grant revenue is recognized to the extent of the related expenses.

Grant and contract expenses are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. Current period expenses are reduced for grant refunds and overappropriations.

Investments and investment income

Short-term investments are recorded at cost which approximates market. Investment income is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs of the Council have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Costs which cannot be specifically identified with a particular program area are distributed evenly to all programs.

Furniture and equipment

The costs of office furniture and equipment are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be sufficiently material to warrant capitalization and depreciation.

Note 3—Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's retirement annuity program, which is administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution amounted to \$61,000 and \$66,000 for fiscal years 1984 and 1983, respectively.

Note 4—Commitments

The Council entered into a lease agreement for office space expiring in 1987 which may be cancelled with one year notice. The minimum future rentals as of June 30, 1984 are approximately \$135,000 for fiscal years 1985 and 1986 and \$124,000 for fiscal year 1987.

In September 1982, the Council entered into an agreement to sub-lease a portion of its leased office space. The rent income from the sub-lease amounted to approximately \$28,000 in fiscal year 1984 and was used to offset office rent expense.

Program Guidelines and Grant Application Procedures

The Council on Library Resources (CLR) is a private operating foundation that has since 1956 encouraged efforts to improve library service, library operations, and the quality of information systems. CLR concentrates on academic and research libraries because of their importance to scholarship, higher education, and the public interest.

Grants are awarded to organizations and individuals for projects related to CLR objectives. As an operating foundation, the Council also initiates and manages its own programs. Occasionally, the Council enters into contractual arrangements.

CLR often acts as a catalyst, bringing together expert individuals and representatives of organizations to explore specific issues. The Council also serves as a coordinating agent for cooperative undertakings, and provides consultation services where help is needed but funding is not sought or not possible.

Current program interests include enhancing, preserving and extending access to library resources; bibliographic services; the management and economics of libraries, and professional education. The Council does not entertain proposals for the construction or renovation of buildings, purchase or preservation of collections, equipment purchases, or routine operating costs. In general, the objective is to support programs that benefit many institutions, and grants are not provided for work that focuses on the needs of a single library. As a matter of policy, no funds are provided to defray indirect costs.

Application Procedures

Inquiries regarding support should be in the form of a letter that includes the following information:

1. The name and address of the individual or organization initiating the request, the name of the proposed principal investigator, and a one-paragraph abstract of the proposal.
2. Type of institution and tax status.
3. A concise statement of the aims and significance of the project, including a description of the general approach and research methods to be used.
4. Amount of the request and proposed total budget.
5. Proposed starting date and projected duration of the work.

Each inquiry will be evaluated in terms of its relationship to current CLR priorities. All proposals are reviewed internally in accordance with established procedures. In addition, the Council often requests external reviews of proposals on a confidential basis. If reviews suggest that the proposed work is of interest, additional information will be requested and advice will be offered concerning proposal preparation. There are no deadlines for general grant applications; deadlines for specific program grants are announced in the Council's newsletter, *Recent Developments*, and through press releases.

All inquiries should be addressed to Warren J. Haas, President, Council on Library Resources, Inc., 1785 Massachusetts Ave., N.W. Washington, D.C. 20036.

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